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Research Article

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SUSTAINED VIRAL RESPONSE AT 12 WEEKS (SVR-12) AFTER TREATMENT WITH COMBINATION OF VELPATASVIR 100MG AND SOFOSBUVIR 400MG AMONG NON-CIRRHOTIC AND CIRRHOTIC PATIENTS AT JINNAH HOSPITAL LAHORE¹Dr. Ayesha Akram, ²Dr. Mehreen Naz, ³Dr. Eram Najm¹Allama Iqbal Medical College, Jinnah Hospital Lahore,
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Email: mehrshakil9@gmail.com.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Globally, viral hepatitis C is a significant public health issue with an expected 71 million individuals suffering from hepatitis C around the world[1]. The menace of Hepatitis C is the leading cause of liver failure and liver cancer in 30% to 50% of infected patients worldwide[1,2]. Pakistan carries one of the world's highest burden of end stage liver diseases and mortality due to liver failure and liver cancer, which affects 6 per 100,000 males and 4 per 100,000 females[3]. With an expected prevalence of 4.5-8.2%, Pakistan has the second highest prevalence of hepatitis C after Egypt.

Methodology: Setting: The Study was done at Jinnah hospital Lahore.

Sample size: 93 case of hepatitis C positive per was included in the study.

Sample Selection: Consecutive non-probability sampling

Study design: Randomized control trail

Study setting: The study was conducted at hepatitis clinic, department of medicine Jinnah Hospital Lahore. Data Collection

All the patients was initially screened by rapid testing device (RTDs) for hepatitis C. The patients tested positive for hepatitis C in initial screening was further advised blood sampling for qualitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test.

Results: 95% of non-cirrhotic patients had achieved SVR whereas 89% of cirrhotic patients has achieved SVR. 5% of non-cirrhotic patients had not achieved SVR whereas 11% of cirrhotic patients had not achieved SVR.

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INTRODUCTION:

Globally, viral hepatitis C is a significant public health issue with an expected 71 million individuals suffering from hepatitis C around the world[1]. The menace of Hepatitis C is the leading cause of liver failure and liver cancer in 30% to 50% of infected patients worldwide[1,2]. Pakistan carries one of the world's highest burden of end stage liver diseases and mortality due to liver failure and liver cancer, which affects 6 per 100,000 males and 4 per 100,000 females[3]. With an expected prevalence of 4.5-8.2%, Pakistan has the second highest prevalence of hepatitis C after Egypt[2,3]. The World Health Organisation (WHO) set an objective of eradicating hepatitis C and B disease by 2030 with the goal to a decrease of 65% in death rate and decline of 90% in new cases[1]. These major and substantial targets is achievable through a number of significant measures of instant approach of general public to low cost testing and treatment with the new regime of direct antiviral agents therapy, along with protective measures to prevent infection in high risk groups and halting the reuse of syringes [3,4]. While there has been some promising advancement in worldwide treatment scale-up with above 3 million people successfully completed the treatment with direct anti viral agents (DAAs) since 2015[6,7]. However, in developing countries with poor healthcare settings, under 10% of total chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infected cases is diagnosed due to poor testing and diagnostic facilities. The elimination of hepatitis by 2030 would only be achieved through the emergence of highly efficacious and low side effects antiviral drugs which would readily available in affordable price, single administered dosage and required little or no monitoring[7].

Different treatment regimes had been initially developed such as interferon and pegylated interferon with or without ribavirin in late twentieth century, but sustained viral response (SVR) could not be achieved more than 45% in genotype 1, 80% in genotype 2 and 50% in genotype 3a patients[5,6]. Meanwhile, half of these patients have been relapsed after the initial response. Moreover, 60% of patients were non-responder to these regimes[6]. Low SVR rates with interferon related side effects such as depression of bone marrow, autoimmune and neuropsychiatric disorders have led the researchers to develop new safe and effective drug therapies[8]. The newer direct acting antiviral (DAA) drugs has revolutionised the treatment of hepatitis C infection due to its great efficacy, low cost and short treatment course[8,9]. The development of direct acting antiviral agents (DAA) has significantly improved the sustained viral response

(SVR) of 90% and greater irrespective of treatment experienced, hepatic fibrosis and demographic variables[14].

METHODOLOGY:

Setting: The Study was done at Jinnah hospital Lahore.

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Inclusive criteria:

1. Patient aged 18-55 years
2. Patient of both gender
3. Patients who had past failed treatment with Sofosbuvir/Ribavirin or Sofosbuvir/NS3 inhibitor

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients having sign of decompensation of liver (hematemesis, melena and/or ascites)
2. Patients having co-infection with hepatitis B and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)
3. Patients with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC)
4. Ultrasound findings include ascites, portal vein thrombosis, nodule > 3mm and shrunken liver
5. Patients with prior NS5A inhibitor therapy

Data collection procedure:

After approval from hospital ethical committee, patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria was enrolled in this study from Hepatitis clinic, Department of Medicine, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. Informed consent was obtained and patient demographic information (name, age, gender) was recorded. Patients were placed in two groups after detection of hepatitis C viral RNA on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test into cirrhotic and non-cirrhotic categories depending upon their laboratory and radiological investigations. Both groups was treated by the combination of the newer direct antiviral agents of velpatasvir 100mg and sofosbuvir 400mg drug therapy for 12 weeks. The sustained viral response after 12 weeks (SVR-12) of velpatasvir 100mg and sofosbuvir 400mg was analysed with the help of polymerase chain reaction test (PCR) and questionnaire. The research indexes included patient's age, body mass index (BMI), smoking history, hypertension and diabetes mellitus.

All the patients was initially screened by rapid testing device (RTDs) for hepatitis C. The patients tested

positive for hepatitis C in initial screening was further advised blood sampling for qualitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test. The patients having hepatitis C viral RNA detected on polymerase chain reaction test (PCR) fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria was considered in my study. The baseline laboratory investigations (complete blood count, liver function test and renal function tests) were performed of all these diagnosed hepatitis C. These patients was divided into two categories of non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic depending on their abdominal ultrasound findings, aspartate transaminase AST to platelet ratio index (APRI) score and fibrosis 4 (Fib-4) score .

AST to Platelet Ratio Index (APRI) Score was used for every patient with a lower cut-off value of 0.5 and a upper cut-off value of 2[17,18]. We will use 40 IU/L as the value for the AST upper limit of normal when calculating an APRI value as recommended by most experts[17]. The patient values of aspartate transaminase and platelet count was be used to calculate the APRI Score. Fibrosis 4 (Fib-4) Score with a lower cut-off value of 1.45 and upper cut-off value of 3.25 was used in our study using normal values of alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase, platelet count and age[19]. The patient having the APRI score less than 0.5 and Fib-4 score less than 1.45 was categorised as non-cirrhotic. The patient having the APRI score greater than 2 and Fib-4 score greater than 3.25 was defined as cirrhotic. The patients having APRI Score between 0.5 and 2 and Fib-4 score between 1.45 and 3.25 was categorised as non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic on ultrasound and fibro scan finding[19]. The liver with smooth surface, normal texture, no nodularity and size less than 15cm on ultrasound was considered as non-cirrhotic. The liver having coarse texture, nodules less than 3mm and size greater than 15cm was included in cirrhotic category. The patients having unremarkable findings on ultrasound was allocated non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic categories based on fibro scan results.

Group A: include non-cirrhotic patients on ultrasound findings with receive single dose of velpatasvir 100mg and sofosbuvir 400mg combination for 12 weeks.

Group B: include cirrhotic patients on ultrasound findings will take single dose of velpatasvir 100mg and sofosbuvir 400mg combination for 12 weeks.

Patients was be asked to take study medication once at the same time each day. The treatment was discontinued if signs of decompensation of liver (hematemesis, melena and/or ascites) develop. The patient was followed 4 weekly with complete blood count (CBC), liver function test (LFT) and renal function test (RFT) to assess the efficacy of the drug. The patients was tested for hepatitis C viral RNA by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test after 12 weeks on completion of the treatment to check the sustained viral response (SVR 12). The two groups was compared for the sustained viral response of the velpatasvir and sofosbuvir combination therapy after the 12 weeks. Detection of hepatitis C viral RNA by polymerase chain reaction test after 12 weeks of treatment was considered as treatment failure. Discontinuation of treatment due to signs of decompensation of liver was considered as treatment failure.

RESULTS:

Total of 93 patients were included in the study. 40 of those patients were cirrhotic and 53 patients were non cirrhotic. Mean age was 49.4 (\pm 12.1) years with male to female ratio of 1.1 (114/102). Liver disease was already de-compensated in 17.1% patients whereas 3 had history of encephalopathy. Diabetes mellitus was present in 14.4% patients and 12% were hypertensive. Treatment naïve patients were 68.1% and 31.9% were treatment experienced patients. 95% of non-cirrhotic patients had achieved SVR whereas 89% of cirrhotic patients has achieved SVR. 5% of non-cirrhotic patients had not achieved SVR whereas 11% of cirrhotic patients had not achieved SVR.

Comparison of HCV patients with SVR12 and those who failed to achieve SVR12.

Variables	Patients with SVR12	NO SVR12	P value
Age (years)	49.2 (\pm 12.5)	50 (\pm 11)	0.53
Duration of illness (months)	50.6 (\pm 48.2)	58.3 (\pm 58.4)	0.58
Platelet count (x 10 ⁹ /L)	182.7 (\pm 86)	143.5 (\pm 69.7)	0.50
INR	1.06 (\pm 0.13)	1.24 (\pm 0.4)	0.32
Serum bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.83 (\pm 0.54)	1.16 (\pm 0.99)	0.83

DISCUSSION:

Sofosbuvir has been the first nucleotide analog NS5B polymerase inhibitor tested in 2010 which help to achieve better SVR rate in combination with PEGylated interferon and ribavirin HCV infected cases of genotype 2 or 3[11]. The US Food and Medication Organization (FDA) licenced the use of oral combination of sofosbuvir 400mg and velpatasvir 100mg as a single tablet regime (STR) for the treatment of chronic non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic patients for all 6 genotypes in June 2016[10]. Velpatasvir is a pan-genotypic nucleotide analog NS5A polymerase inhibitor, which is administered in combination with sofosbuvir for 12 weeks in the treatment of hepatitis C viral infection irrespective of the genotype of the hepatitis virus [11]. The testing of the genotype of the hepatitis virus become absolute after the development of these pan-genotypic direct anti viral drugs, thereby eliminating the burden of the cost of genotype tests[12]. This therapy has a excellent sustain viral response at 12 weeks (SVR-12) of greater than 95% for all 6 genotypes of hepatitis virus with good safety profile in phase III clinical trials[12,13]. All the non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic patients do not need monitoring while treating with Velpatasvir 100mg and Sofosbuvir 400mg for 12 weeks therapy. Whereas decompensated patients require close monitoring with this treatment regime[13]. The European Association for Study of Liver Disease (EASL) 2018 guidelines recommended the combination of sofosbuvir-velpatasvir for the cure of both treatment-naive and treatment-experienced hepatitis C infected patients without cirrhosis or with compensated cirrhosis for all 6 HCV genotypes[12].

The rationale of my study is that many international studies have depicted that the efficacy of velpatasvir and sofosbuvir combination is greater in non-cirrhotic HCV patients as compared to cirrhotic patients determined by sustained viral response after 12 weeks (SVR-12) of treatment. In Pakistan, very few evidence based studies has been conducted to evaluate the efficacy and safety profile of the sofosbuvir-velpatasvir combination since its approval in March 2018[15]. The only local study done up till now in our healthcare facilities involve small sample size of non-cirrhotic (95 patients) and cirrhotic (38 patients). This study showed SVR-12 rate of 90.5% and 92.1% among non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic patients respectively[16]. The prospective interventional trial in my study will determining the sustained viral response after 12 weeks of treatment with Velpatasvir 100mg and Sofosbuvir 400mg combination in hepatitis C patients without cirrhosis and with compensated cirrhosis along with the validation of

APRI/FIB-4 scores to differentiate the non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic patients in the local population. This study was first on large sample size to document efficacy of velpatasvir and sofosbuvir combination among non-cirrhotic and cirrhotic patients that will not only delineate guidelines for physicians but also was beneficial to reduce morbidity and cost of HCV patients treatment.

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